

Storytellers by Design: Critical Approaches to Curating Research-Driven Digital Experiences Using Design Methods

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Introduction and Scientific Scope

For many humanities professionals, digital storytelling has become a rewarding strategy for showcasing their research across different medial environments. It builds up on traditional storytelling elements and techniques, such as actors, setting, music, voice and emotion, and utilises any combination of digitally available media like images, sound, video, maps, 3D models and interactive elements (Alexander 2017; Wu and Chen 2020; Europeana 2025). In this multimodal format, digital storytelling acts as a bridge between research and stakeholders, allowing scholars to translate their findings into relevant stories for a diverse audience (Barber 2016; Earley-Spadoni 2017; Yee and Stevens 2019). In this way, researchers are afforded the opportunity to experiment with non-traditional forms of communication, conveying ideas, emotions, and spatial understanding in a layered narrative that extends the written text to make information not just visible, but experiential and memorable.

However, despite this “digital” component, the emphasis is primarily on the story and the telling, prioritising the narrative over engagement with technology. At the same time, translating research into effective multimodal narratives involves more than familiarity with tools or technical proficiency. It entails considerations for critical digital literacy (CDL) on the part of both the storyteller and the story-receiver, placing an emphasis on the skills and competencies for critically engaging with different digital media, tools, and technologies (Hauck 2025). For digital humanists, CDL translates as the recognition of the cultural, political, epistemological, and ethical implications of these tools for knowledge production, representation, and power (Dobson 2019; Viola 2023). In a digital storytelling context, this involves the digital creators to reflect on the role of technology when curating narrative. Following these principles, the execution of a successful digital story requires a carefully designed process in which audience needs, context and interpretive goals take priority. Choices about what to (and not to) include, how to build the narrative, which medium best serves the content, and how to balance scholarly depth with accessibility, among many others, are crucial considerations when implementing the digital output.

To address these decisions, a design-thinking, human-centred approach offers a structured way to engage in digital storytelling as critical research practice. Whereas design thinking is a philosophical mindset that foregrounds a creative, process-driven and experimental approach to tackling complex problems, design methods are the translation of the design-thinking process into

hands-on tasks or activities, such as developing personas, storyboards or journey maps (Digital Society School n.d.). While design thinking is well established in DH pedagogy, this workshop extends its use beyond project planning by demonstrating how specific design methods (personas, journey mapping, narrative decomposition) can function as reflective scholarly tools.

In digital storytelling practice, this begins with an understanding of your audience and how they derive meaning from stories, rather than starting with a selection of preferred technology or data, the process then moves through iterative cycles that involve empathising with the final user, defining core problems or challenges, ideating solutions, prototyping the digital story, and testing outputs. As a toolkit for design thinking, design methods offer researchers an ideal framework for instrumentalising the reflexive critical decision-making process allowing them to deconstruct complex scholarly work and design compelling, research-driven stories.

Aim

This workshop advances an emerging methodological perspective by positioning digital storytelling not merely as a communication strategy but as a research method in its own right. Participants do not simply learn to “apply” design thinking; instead, they use design methods as analytical instruments to interrogate how narrative, multimodality, and digital form shape scholarly interpretation, argumentation, and meaning-making within humanities research. Through a conceptual framing of critical digital literacy in action, participants become both evaluator and curator of digital narratives. They will learn how to apply design thinking methods to the iterative cycle of project planning, thereby learning to evaluate and guide digital narratives, understanding how choices about content, format, and presentation influence the way research is experienced and interpreted.

The workshop also demonstrates that digital literacy does not require advanced technical skillsets. Digital storytelling tools increasingly emphasize user-experience design, ensuring these tools are accessible and inclusive for humanities researchers of any digital competency. Reporting and experiences show that the most challenging part of effective digital storytelling is not technological sophistication and expertise (e.g., Gibbs and Owen 2012; Warwick 2012; Tracy 2016). Rather, it is a critical understanding of the affordances and limitations of digital platforms and finding creative ways to convey meaning within these constraints.

Finally, the workshop highlights the value of open science communication to the wider scholarly community, and marks it as a shared responsibility to leverage these tools and platforms for transferring knowledge to others in engaging and digestible formats. Whether it is about objects, texts, people, places or landscapes, all humanities research at every stage of the process can be transformed into a research-driven narrative and anyone can become a storyteller. We therefore aim that participants will leave the workshop with practical strategies for planning, designing, and evaluating their own research-driven stories, which can be applied to teaching, public engagement or future projects.

Preliminary Program

1. Opening Presentation (20 mins)
 - Introduction to digital storytelling concepts and different modalities for curating research-driven DH narratives, with examples of open-source, user-friendly platform options.
 - Overview of core principles of critical digital literacy for engaging with multimodal scholarship.
2. Small group activity and discussion (40 mins)
 - Small groups are provided with an example of a humanities-related digital storytelling output.
 - Through a design-thinking activity, they will evaluate and critically examine the output's content and format to unpack perspective, tone and message, noting how the user-experience impacts these aspects.
 - Each group reports back their analysis in a plenary discussion.
3. Break (15 mins)
4. Presentation on Design Thinking Methods for DH (15 mins)
 - Introduction to design thinking methods and how it can be extended to the creation process in the design, implementation and evaluation stages of digital storytelling.
5. Case Study Project (60 mins)
 - Two hands-on design thinking activities for planning a research-driven digital narrative experience.
 - Activities will structure the group's consideration of decision factors relating to medial affordances, interactivity, thematic topics, audience, ethics, dissemination strategies and a plan for gathering feedback.
6. Concluding Plenary (30 mins)
 - Mini-presentations by the groups to share their decision-making process for the project
 - Share final insights and how to transfer the concepts and skills to future work

Expected Outcomes

Expected outcomes for the workshop participants include:

- A broad overview of digital storytelling principles and existing open-source tools and platforms, with links to self-directed online learning resources.
- Exposure to design methods which they can re-use in their own collaborative project-planning activities, in teaching or for gathering user feedback.

- New skills for engaging in critical digital evaluation for reflecting on the affordances, limitations and implications of digital design decisions.
- A practical guide and roadmap for digital storytelling project planning, transferring the workshop skills beyond the conference venue.
- Inspiration to examine their research from unique perspectives, e.g., how can methodological approaches or data collection processes be transformed into an engaging narrative.
- A clearer understanding of digital storytelling as a methodological practice that contributes to research design, interpretive argumentation, and scholarly reflexivity, extending beyond skills training into conceptual innovation within DH methods.

Target Audience

This workshop is designed for researchers, heritage professionals, educators and students in history, archaeology and related humanities disciplines, seeking a broad exposure to current digital storytelling modalities and design thinking approaches to transfer into their own work or teaching activities. This workshop is especially relevant for participants who are planning a digital storytelling output for their current or upcoming project.

Format and Logistics

To facilitate a collaborative environment for the small group hands-on design activities, we propose a fully in-person format. As a half-day workshop, we expect the workshop to last for three hours and can accommodate around 25 participants. Laptops or tablets are recommended.

Participants are encouraged to bring their own research topics and materials for the case-study part of the workshop. They should contact the organisers in advance to see necessary requirements for this. Alternative examples will nevertheless be prepared as case study projects.

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